

Dioxouranium(VI) and Thorium(IV) Complexes with a Tri-dentate Ligand

HRUDANANDA MOHANTA* AND KAILASH C. DASH†

Department of Chemistry, Bhadrak College, Bhadrak-756 100, India

Manuscript received 17 August 1979, accepted 30 November 1979

New dioxouranium(VI) and thorium(IV) complexes with a dibasic tri-dentate ligand, H_2L , derived by the condensation of anthranilic acid and salicylaldehyde were prepared and characterised. The ligand behaved as a neutral one when reacted with UO_2X_n forming 10-coordinated complexes of the type $UO_2(H_2L)_nX_n$ ($X=Cl, I, NCS, NO_3, ClO_4, 0.5SO_4$) and with UO_2Ac_2 it formed 8-coordinated $UO_2(HL)_2$, acting as a deprotonated, uninegative, tridentate ligand. The latter form of coordination also takes place on reaction with ThX_4 to form complexes of the type $Th(HL)_nX_n \cdot nH_2O$ ($X=Cl, I, NCS, NO_3, ClO_4$ and $n=2, 3$ or 4). These water molecules are only loosely held by the metal ion and all of them are lost on heating at 120° . The Th(IV) complexes are thus all 8-coordinated.

COMPOUNDS of amino acids with transition metal ions are well known¹, but those of the Schiff bases of amino acids are not as common². Further, not many Schiff base complexes of the 4f- or 5f-inner transition elements are known^{3,4}. Very rarely, the Schiff bases coordinate as the neutral molecules, the usual form being the deprotonated anions of the Schiff base. As a part of our study of dioxouranium(VI) and thorium(IV) complexes with multi-dentate ligands having 2 to 6 donor sites, we have already reported⁵⁻⁷ complexes with several Schiff bases and now report the synthesis and characterisation of a series of complexes with a potential tridentate ligand, anthranilic acid salicylidene imine H_2L (donor set NO_2) derived by the condensation of salicylaldehyde and anthranilic acid. The ligand coordinates either as a neutral molecule to form complexes $UO_2(H_2L)_nX_n$ ($X=Cl, I, NCS, NO_3, ClO_4, 0.5SO_4$) or as a uninegative ion (HL^-) to form complexes of the type $UO_2(HL)_2$ or $Th(HL)_2X_n \cdot nH_2O$ ($X=Cl, I, NCS, NO_3, ClO_4$). The compounds have been characterised by analytical data, electrical conductivity and IR spectral measurements, and the stoichiometry as well as the coordination number assigned.

Experimental

Hydrated thorium(IV) and uranyl(VI) chloride, nitrate and uranyl sulphate were B.D.H. reagent grade. The iodide, thiocyanate, perchlorate of uranyl(VI) and thorium(IV) were prepared as described earlier⁵⁻⁷.

The ligand anthranilic acid salicylaldehyde (H_2L) was prepared by adding an alcoholic solution of salicylaldehyde dropwise to an ethanolic solution of anthranilic acid. The resulting orange solution

was refluxed for 6 hours and on slow evaporation the desired orange-red crystalline compound separated out, which was filtered washed several times with alcohol and dried in *vacuo*.

The C, H, N analyses were carried out at Würzburg University, W. Germany. The metal (uranium and thorium) and the anion (Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , ClO_4^- , SO_4^{2-}) were estimated as described⁵⁻⁷. The electrical conductivity, IR spectra and electronic spectra were measured as usual⁵.

Preparation of the complexes :

The complexes were prepared by mixing, warm ethanolic solution of the appropriate metal salt with the ligand in ethanol medium (1:2.5 ratio). In almost all cases the complexes appeared on stirring and in few cases refluxing was required. The complexes were filtered, washed with alcohol followed by ether and dried in *vacuo*. The anhydrous thorium(IV) complexes were prepared by keeping the hydrated complexes in an air-oven at 120° for several hours to constant weight.

Results and Discussion

The complexes isolated are presented in Tables 1 and 2 alongwith their characterising data. All the compounds have an intense yellow or orange-yellow colour, they are high melting ($>260^\circ$) and quite stable. The electrical conductance values in CH_3NO_2 or DMF solutions adequately confirmed the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes⁸. The electronic spectra in methanol were found to be similar to each other in regard to band shapes and positions. The Th(IV) complexes contain either 2,3 or 4 molecules of water of crystallisation and all

† Present address : Anorg. Chem. Inst. Technischen Universität München, Lichtenbergstr-4, D-8046, Garching, W. Germany.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISING DATA FOR
DIOXOURANIUM(VI) COMPLEXES

Compound	Analyses(%) Found (calc.)					Δ_m in MeNO ₃ (Ω^{-1} mole ⁻¹ cm ²)
	U	C	H	N	X	
UO ₂ (H ₂ L) ₂ Cl ₂	29.2 (28.9)	40.4 (40.8)	2.8 (2.6)	3.7 (3.4)	8.4 (8.6)	11.5
UO ₂ (H ₂ L) ₂ I ₂	23.8 (23.6)	33.1 (33.4)	2.2 (2.1)	2.5 (2.7)	25.0 (25.3)	15.0
UO ₂ (H ₂ L) ₂ (NCS) ₂	27.4 (27.4)	41.7 (41.4)	2.4 (2.5)	6.0 (6.4)	13.3 (13.3)	20.6
UO ₂ (H ₂ L) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	27.5 (27.1)	38.0 (38.3)	2.5 (2.5)	6.5 (6.3)	14.0 (14.1)	21.2
UO ₂ (H ₂ L) ₂ SO ₄	28.4 (28.0)	39.2 (39.6)	2.4 (2.5)	3.4 (3.3)	11.5 (11.3)	44*
UO ₂ (H ₂ L) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	27.5 (28.0)	39.1 (39.4)	2.6 (2.5)	3.0 (3.2)	23.1 (23.3)	10.7
UO ₂ (HL) ₂	32.0 (31.7)	44.5 (44.7)	2.8 (2.6)	3.5 (3.7)	—	3.4*

* Conductance values in DMF.

$\nu(C \equiv N)$ and $\nu(C-S)$ vibrations of a *N*-coordinated terminally bonded isothiocyanate¹⁰. The nitrate complexes exhibit bands at 1460, 1280, 1045, 820 and 730 cm⁻¹ showing evidences for unidentate coordination (C_{3v}) of the nitro group¹¹. The bidentate coordination of the sulphato group^{12,13} (C_{2v}) in UO₂(H₂L)SO₄ is evident from the appearance of the bands at 1175, 1155, 1075 and 650 and 610 cm⁻¹ regions. The UO₂(H₂L)₂(ClO₄)₂ and the Th(HL)₂(ClO₄)₂ complexes contain the ClO₄⁻ group which are coordinated in a unidentate manner¹⁴ as is clear from their IR spectra observed at 1135, 1110, 1020 and 620 cm⁻¹ region.

Thus, a series of uranyl complexes having a coordination number of 8 or 10 and a series of thorium(IV) complexes having a coordination number of 8, are isolated where the ligand is coordinated in a tri-dentate manner either as neutral molecule or as a deprotonated, uninegative anion.

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISING DATA FOR THORIUM(IV) COMPLEXES

Compound	Analyses(%) Found (calc.)					%loss of H ₂ O at 120°C	Δ_m in MeNO ₃ (Ω^{-1} mol ⁻¹ cm ²)
	Th	C	H	N	X		
Th(HL) ₂ Cl ₂ .4H ₂ O	26.5 (26.2)	39.0 (39.2)	3.1 (3.2)	3.3 (3.2)	8.3 (8.0)	8.1 (8.1)	10
Th(HL) ₂ I ₂ .2H ₂ O	22.5 (22.7)	33.1 (33.5)	2.2 (2.3)	2.5 (2.7)	25.0 (25.3)	3.5 (3.5)	14
Th(HL) ₂ (NCS) ₂ .2H ₂ O	27.0 (26.9)	42.1 (42.5)	3.0 (2.8)	6.3 (6.6)	13.4 (13.7)	4.2 (4.2)	51
Th(HL) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ .3H ₂ O	26.4 (26.0)	37.9 (37.6)	3.0 (2.8)	6.1 (6.2)	13.4 (13.9)	5.9 (6.0)	9
Th(HL) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂ .2H ₂ O	24.1 (24.5)	35.7 (35.4)	2.8 (2.5)	3.1 (3.0)	21.5 (21.1)	3.7 (3.8)	9

of them are lost quantitatively by heating the hydrated complexes at 120°. They are not bound to the metal ion as is clear from the IR spectra of the hydrated complexes.

The IR spectra of the ligand and the complexes were investigated. In all cases $\nu(OH)$ was obtained as a weak band in 3300-3400 cm⁻¹ region, $\nu(C \equiv N)$ in the 1610-1625 cm⁻¹ region, $\nu(C-O)$ in the 1180 cm⁻¹ region, $\nu_{as}(COO^-)$ in 1590 cm⁻¹ region and $\nu_s(COO^-)$ in the 1380-1410 cm⁻¹ region. In addition, $\nu(C-N)$ at 1270 cm⁻¹, $\nu(C-H)$ at around 3000 cm⁻¹ and the phenyl ring vibrations at 1500 cm⁻¹ region were observed. These indicate the tri-dentate coordination of the ligand in the complexes. The uranyl vibrations were observed at about 920 cm⁻¹ and 810 cm⁻¹ corresponding to $\nu_{as}(U-O)$ and $\nu_s(U-O)$ vibrations, respectively⁹ in good agreement with the linear nature of the UO₂²⁺ group.

The thiocyanate complexes exhibit bands at 2040 and 835 cm⁻¹ for the dioxouranium(VI) complex and at 2050, 2030 and 840 cm⁻¹ for the thorium(IV) complex corresponding to the

Acknowledgement

Our thanks are due to F. E. Ullrich, Anorg. Chem. Institut, Würzburg (W. Germany) for carrying out the C, H, N analyses of all the compounds.

References

1. K. NAKAMOTO, Y. NORIMOTO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4528.
2. R. H. HOLM, G. W. EVERETT, JR. and A. CHAKRAVORTY *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, (Ed. F. A. COTTON, Wiley, New York, 1966, Vol. 7, p. 83).
3. A. E. COMYNS, *Chem. Rev.*, 1960, **60**, 115.
4. A. K. MUKHERJEA and P. RAY, *J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 166.
5. H. N. MOHANTA and K. C. DASH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15A**, 657; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 166.
6. H. N. MOHANTA and K. C. DASH, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1345; *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1978, **8**, 43.

J. INDIAN CHEM. SOC., VOL. LVII, JANUARY 1980

7. K. C. DASH and H. N. MOHANTA, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1977, **2**, 229.
8. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Revs.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
9. J. I. BULLOCK and F. W. PARETT, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1970, **48**, 3095.
10. R. A. BAILEY, S. L. KOZAK, T. W. MICHRISEN and W. N. MILLS, *Coord. Chem. Revs.*, 1971, **6**, 407.
11. M. CHOCA and J. R. FERRARO, *J. Chem. Soc., (Dalton)*, 1972, 2297.
12. G. C. BARRACLOUGH and M. L. TOBE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 1993.
13. E. P. HERTZENBERG and J. C. BAILAR, JR., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 2371.
14. B. J. HATHAWAY and A. E. UNDERHILL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3091.